

METHODS OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IMPROVING READING IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN HIGH SCHOOL

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Abstract. This article is about some interactive games that can be used to increase efficiency in English language classes, their use cases, organization, and expected effectiveness.

Keywords: Interactive game, efficiency, didactic, interactive method, "Change your seats", "Cooky jar".

МЕТОДЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИГРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ЧТЕНИЯ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ИНОСТРАННОМУ В ВУЗЕ

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена некоторым интерактивным играм, которые можно использовать для повышения эффективности занятий по английскому языку, их вариантам использования, организации и ожидаемой эффективности.

Ключевые слова: Интерактивная игра, эффективность, дидактика, интерактивный метод, «Пересаживайтесь», «Баночка с печеньем».

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-growing time, science, technology are also growing rapidly. Progress in each area is taking a step forward. In particular, great changes, significant achievements are also being made in science. The delivery of each subject to students using new innovative technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education.

Today there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. From them, the effectiveness of the lesson will be higher if extensive and different methods of covering the topic are used in the lessons, and an increase in the interest of the student in the lesson will also be ensured. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by bringing innovations into the educational process and their implementation. The use of various role-playing, action games in the teaching of foreign language lessons causes an increased interest in language learning, both in the lesson. And through the work of students in pairs or small groups, it helps students to communicate communicatively with others.

Today, teaching in schools through interactive games is becoming a tradition. As you know, the passage of the lesson based on various games ensures that students can demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become strong. The basis of the use of gaming technology is activity that activates and accelerates the reader. Psychologists note that the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of the individual for self-expression, finding a stable place in life, self-control, the implementation of their capabilities.

On the basis of any game, the generally accepted principles of Education, tactics should lie. Educational subjects should be taken as a basis for educational games. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a simple lesson and freely operates. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested.

The experience suggests that in any game, regardless of the qualifications and age of the participants, they will fall into a stalemate state. Therefore, before applying the game to

educational practice, it is necessary to solve the following pedagogical and psychological issues. Every reader should know the following when preparing for the game:

- ✓ aim of the game;
- ✓ function of the game;
- ✓ what theme The Game concerns in the plan;
- ✓ the ability to apply the skills and skills formed in previous games even in

subsequent ones.

MAIN PART

We know that in the current educational jargon, the student must be a subject. In doing so, focusing on more interactive techniques increases learning efficiency. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach independent thinking.

In particular, in the process of teaching a foreign language, a lot of pressure and burden falls on language learners. For this reason, many students cannot effectively master foreign language lessons. One of the most effective ways to alleviate this condition and reduce the pressure that students feel is to use unconventional methods in the course process, especially interactive games like the one mentioned above. In the process of interactive games, the main task is performed by the students themselves. The teacher, on the other hand, acts in this process only as a guide, a process controller.

How interesting and effective, subject-appropriate, didactic content the lesson retains depends primarily on the pedagogical skills and creativity of the teacher. Any teacher also tries to use interactive techniques in his lessons using internet resources, manuals, personal experiences of colleagues. But in this process, special attention should also be paid to individual characteristics. For example, the age of students, the level of assimilation, personal and psychological characteristics, the size of the room in which the lesson will be held, equipment, etc. Below we will briefly talk about several interactive games and their advantages, organizational process.

“**Change your seats**” is a game designed to be played in a spacious room, with a large number of students, and can be used for the upper classes on related fragmentary topics such as quality levels, present and past tense forms of correct and incorrect verbs. In elementary grades, however, it is possible to transfer in parts such as letters and words that start with that letter, the written names of objects, animals or Numbers and their drawings.

Let's consider this game on the example of the topic of quality levels in the upper classes. First of all, the topic of quality levels should be explained in the last lesson, and memorizing the list of levels of adjectives should be given to the house as a task. To start the game, students will be able to sit in a circle, face to face each other. The teacher gives in the hands of each participant a card with one word, that is, an adjective. In this case, three different levels of one quality will be in three separate cards. In order for the game to be organized correctly, it is desirable that the number of students be 15-18. One participant comes out in the middle of the circle. In 30 seconds, students will have to show each other their cards, look at each other's cards, find the other two parts of the quality on their cards, and recognize those card holders as partners. When the time is up, the teacher says different words. When you say a word about the category of quality, students will have to change places with their partners. And the reader standing in the middle will have to find an empty chair and sit down. In this way, the process is repeated several times. And then the cards are collected, other cards are given, and the game starts again from the very beginning. This game is useful for students' grammatical knowledge and listening comprehension skills. Because the game process is fun, students can easily memorize quality levels. From my own personal experience, students in the 7th grade have memorized more than 30 quality levels after 3 lessons. Depending on the didactic material, this game can also be used on other topics.

“Cooky jar”. This game is also considered to be widely popular games. It will be a very interesting process, especially if it is organized in elementary grades with colored handouts. This game is directly related to the song, and pet names are listed throughout the song, which is especially useful for reinforcing the theme of pets. At the beginning of the lesson, each student is given cards with the same pictures of pets. When singing, each reader should indicate which pet is being told, the same animal picture card. Cards with the name of the pet can also be added to this. After hearing it several times, readers themselves begin to sing and sing the song. It follows that along with the listening comprehension skills of students, speaking skills also develop. At this time, vocabulary also increases. This game can also be adapted to other themes by changing the song. The most important thing is a very interesting process for students, making language learning even easier and creating a creative mult.

“Translator”. Another interactive game that develops the skill of speaking in students is the game “translator”, in which the teacher plays the role of an alien. Readers, on the other hand, must explain to him the meaning of each item or word. In this game, students’ improvisation skills are formed, and by performing various actions, acting skills are also formed. It also encourages students to think in a special way. This game is mostly more accessible to upper-class students, where they will have a certain amount of vocabulary and students will use them.

CONCLUSION

All of the above games can be applied to make the English learning process more fun. And the most important thing is that the games, techniques used in the course of the lesson will pay off, and students will further develop their language skills.

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